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2 Sexual size dimorphism in Manakins elsie.shogren@rochester.edu

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4 **Supplementary Figures and Tables:**5 **Dancing drives evolution of sexual size dimorphism in manakins**

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Figure S1: Relationship between raw (A, B) and natural log transformed (C, D) wing length and species average mass values for males and females. Pearson's product-moment correlations and p-values shown in top left corner of appropriate plot.

Figure S2: Relationship between raw (A, B) and natural log transformed (C, D) tarsus length and species average mass values for males and females. Pearson's product-moment correlations and p-values shown in top left corner of appropriate plot.

Figure S3: Variation in sexual size dimorphism indices for mass, wing length, and tarsus length. Note that number of species varies for each trait. Mass = 22, wing = 19, tarsus =14. When restricted to only 14 species for which we have all three measurements, the pattern of distribution is qualitatively similar.

Figure S4: Sexual size dimorphism indices for mass sexual size dimorphism. Error bars are 95% confidence intervals calculated by bootstrapping 1000 replicated mean values for each sex and calculating index of sexual size dimorphism using those values. Dashed grey lines show point at which males and females are the same size. Phylogeny shown is used in analyses correcting for phylogenetic relationships. Male manakin illustrations reproduced with the permission of Lynx Edicions.

Figure S5: Sexual size dimorphism indices for tarsus (A) and wing (B). Error bars are 95% confidence intervals calculated by bootstrapping 1000 replicated mean values for each sex and calculating index of sexual size dimorphism using those values. Dashed grey lines show point at which males and females are the same size. Phylogeny shown is used in analyses correcting for phylogenetic relationships.

Figure S6: Test of Rensch's rule, major axis regression of phylogenetic independent contrasts for ln-transformed male and female mass (A), wing length (B), and tarsus length (C). Calculated slope and 95% confidence interval shown in parentheses in the top left corner of appropriate plot. Solid blue line is major axis regression line, forced through 0, dashed black line is unity.

Figure S7: Additional test of association between magnitude of sexual size dimorphism in wing length (A) and tarsus length (B) and species average mass. Pearson's product-moment correlations and p-values shown in top left corner of appropriate plot.

Figure S8: Phylomorphospace plot of mass sexual size dimorphism and agility score, with underlying phylogenetic tree used in analysis connecting taxa. Species name abbreviations are shown in Table S1.

A

B

Figure S9: Relationship between PC2 (environmental variables associated with precipitation) and wing sexual size dimorphism (A) and tarsus sexual size dimorphism (B). Points are not phylogenetically corrected, but lines are extracted from the top phylogenetic generalized least squares model for each response variable: assuming a Brownian motion mode of evolution (A) and assuming Pagel's lambda is equal to zero (B).

A

B

Figure S10: Relationship between agility score and wing sexual size dimorphism (A) and tarsus sexual size dimorphism (B). Points are not phylogenetically corrected, but lines are extracted from the top phylogenetic generalized least squares model for each response variable: assuming a Brownian motion mode of evolution (A) and assuming Pagel's lambda is equal to zero (B).

Table S1: Summary of morphological data analysed for each species

Species (abbreviation)	Mass SSD	Wing SSD	Tarsus SSD	F mass (sd)	M mass (sd)	Species mass	F wing (sd)	M wing (sd)	F tarsus (sd)	M tarsus (sd)	n F	n M	Morph. Source
<i>Neopelma chrysocephalum</i> (N_chr)	0.08	0.07	0.03	15.04 (0.66)	16.35 (0.89)	15.69	66.94 (2.40)	72.25 (2.14)	14.84 (1.46)	15.34 (1.00)	9	56	Ungvári
<i>Lepidothrix serena</i> (L_ser)	-0.05	-0.03	0.05	10.43 (0.68)	9.90 (0.64)	10.17	53.31 (1.12)	51.69 (2.80)	17.83 (0.94)	18.70 (2.22)	75	159	Stouffer
<i>Lepidothrix coronata</i> (L_cor)	-0.14	0.03	0.03	9.85 (1.13)	8.45 (0.68)	9.15	58.12 (2.14)	60.17 (2.30)	14.35 (1.59)	14.81 (1.86)	149	109	White
<i>Cryptopipo holochlora</i> (C_hol)	-0.02	0.04	0.03	16.70 (see [7])	16.30 (see [7])	16.50	65.80 (see [7])	68.70 (see [7])	14.50 (see [7])	15.00 (see [7])	25	39	[7]
<i>Heterocercus aurantiivertex</i> (H_aur)	-0.01	0.03	-0.01	21.05 (1.20)	20.89 (0.27)	20.97	80.00 (3.46)	82.50 (0.71)	14.87 (1.03)	14.70 (1.13)	2	2	Ungvári
<i>Manacus vitellinus</i> (M_vit)	0.11	0.04	0.05	16.91 (3.67)	18.95 (1.78)	17.93	51.33 (11.23)	53.31 (1.04)	20.51 (1.14)	21.48 (0.65)	29	91	Barske
<i>Manacus candei</i> (M_can)	0.05	0.00	...	17.62 (2.09)	18.46 (1.99)	18.04	54.41 (1.29)	54.38 (1.01)	32	20	Boyle
<i>Manacus manacus</i> (M_man)	0.02	...	0.10	16.65 (1.51)	16.99 (1.19)	16.82	19.33 (1.28)	21.36 (0.71)	6	17	Cestari
<i>Pseudopipra pipra</i> (P_pip)	-0.09	0.00	...	13.62 (1.29)	12.43 (1.09)	13.02	61.21 (1.56)	61.19 (1.15)	36	13	Boyle
<i>Ceratopipra erythrocephala</i> (C_ery)	-0.10	-0.03	-0.02	11.97 (0.75)	10.80 (0.99)	11.38	55.83 (1.66)	53.90 (1.53)	16.07 (1.07)	15.70 (0.99)	96	69	Stouffer
<i>Ceratopipra rubrocapilla</i> (C_rub)	0.12	11.75 (1.06)	13.29 (2.02)	12.52	2	8	Anciães
<i>Ceratopipra chloromeros</i> (C_chl)	-0.05	0.00	...	17.16 (1.52)	16.33 (1.21)	16.74	61.05 (2.09)	60.99 (2.40)	107	77	Scholer
<i>Ceratopipra mentalis</i> (C_men)	-0.04	-0.02	...	15.24 (1.24)	14.67 (0.73)	14.96	57.21 (1.33)	56.07 (1.71)	81	34	Boyle
<i>Pipra filicauda</i> (P_fil)	-0.12	0.01	-0.01	15.57 (1.15)	13.64 (0.63)	14.60	63.17 (1.26)	63.93 (1.02)	15.59 (0.60)	15.51 (0.54)	121	216	Ryder
<i>Pipra fasciicauda</i> (P_fas)	-0.04	0.01	...	17.24 (1.58)	16.58 (0.97)	16.91	63.21 (1.95)	63.91 (2.15)	12	23	Scholer
<i>Corapipo altera</i> (C_alt)	-0.14	0.00	...	12.75 (0.92)	11.02 (0.72)	11.88	57.86 (1.70)	57.84 (1.64)	334	615	Boyle
<i>Corapipo gutturalis</i> (C_gut)	-0.13	0.03	-0.04	8.49 (0.79)	7.41 (0.68)	7.95	53.67 (1.32)	55.25 (1.39)	17.14 (0.64)	16.49 (0.72)	23	27	Stouffer
<i>Illicura militaris</i> (I_mil)	-0.03	0.05	0.06	12.52 (0.87)	12.18 (1.04)	12.35	57.02 (1.58)	59.83 (1.76)	17.88 (0.68)	19.03 (0.83)	21	45	Marini

<i>Antilophia bokermanni</i> (A_bok)	0.02	0.02	0.03	20.42 (1.12)	20.91 (1.10)	20.67	73.80 (1.81)	75.30 (3.68)	22.11 (1.16)	22.78 (1.25)	37	29	Gaiotti
<i>Antilophia galeata</i> (A_gal)	-0.01	0.02	0.02	19.10 (3.44)	18.83 (5.12)	18.97	75.13 (2.56)	76.96 (1.54)	21.77 (1.90)	22.32 (1.38)	15	6	Gaiotti
<i>Chiroxiphia pareola</i> (C_par)	-0.04	0.04	-0.02	18.95 (0.96)	18.23 (0.47)	18.59	69.71 (2.14)	72.33 (2.89)	18.71 (1.03)	18.33 (1.20)	6	3	White
<i>Chiroxiphia lanceolata</i> (C_lan)	-0.10	0.03	0.06	19.17 (1.44)	17.26 (1.08)	18.21	69.56 (1.86)	71.34 (1.23)	18.11 (0.49)	19.19 (0.77)	30	32	DuVal

Abbreviation of species name in parentheses is used in other figures. **Mass SSD, Wing SSD, Tarsus SSD** = calculated index of sexual size dimorphism for relevant morphological trait; **F mass (sd), F wing (sd), F tarsus (sd)** = female mass (measured in grams), wing (millimetres), and tarsus (millimetres) averaged for each species, standard deviation in parentheses; **M mass (sd), M wing (sd), and M tarsus (sd)** = male mass averaged for each species, standard deviation in parentheses; **n F** and **n M** = number of females and males for each species; **Morph. source** = author or source providing morphological data.

Grunt-Jump	X						2	2	2														
High and Low Perch-To-Perch Flight Display				1	1					1													
Jump Display										1													
Jump-Snap	X						2	2	2									2					
Partner Pursuit		X															2						
Pip Flight		X																				2	2
'S'-Curve or Swoop-In Flight Display	X			2	2					2	2			2	2	2							
'S'-Curve or Swoop-In Flight Display												1	1										
Semi-circular Jump display		X																2					
Side-To-Side Jump					1						1	1		1	1	1	1						1
Single-Perch Jump w/ About Face							1									1	1						
Somersault							1	1		1													
Squat												1											
Swoop Maneuver										1													1
To-And-Fro Flight		X											2										
To-And-Fro Flight					1		1	1		1		1		1		1	1					1	1

To-and-Fro Jump									1															
Trailing				1			1	1														1	1	
Turn-Around Display										1														
Twist															1									
Up and Down		X																				2	2	
Whirring-To-And-Fro Flight Display	X			2																				
Whirring-To-And-Fro Flight Display				1						1									1					
Agility Score			1	5	10	0	6	7	7	5	10	4	4	7	4	7	6	11	7	7	2	1	11	14
Agility Source		[1-3]	[4,5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[6]	[6]	[9,10]	[6]	[11]	[12]	[21]	[6]	[14,15]	[16]	[17]	[6]	[18]	[19]	[20]	[6]	[6]	

Behaviors are names of display elements described in literature (**Agility Source**) that involved aerial elements and therefore contributed to **Agility Score** used in phylogenetic generalized least squares regression. **S** = sonation and **C** = coordination. Behaviors which contained either of these elements (denoted with an X in the appropriate row) were given a bonus point, and hence have a value of 2 in calculation of species' agility score. Species are abbreviated as first letter of genus, followed by first three letters of species name (refer to Table S1 for full species name and corresponding abbreviation).

Table S3: Phylogenetic principal components of environmental variables

Environmental Variables	pPC1	pPC2
Annual Precipitation	-0.47	-0.85 ^a
Precipitation of Wettest Month	-0.21	-0.58 ^a
Precipitation of Driest Month	-0.46	-0.79 ^a
Precipitation of Warmest Month	0.25	-0.90 ^a
Precipitation of Coldest Month	-0.87 ^a	-0.34
Seasonality of Precipitation	0.45	0.74 ^a
Annual Mean Temperature	-0.84 ^a	0.23
Maximum Temperature	-0.39	0.48
Minimum Temperature	-0.96 ^a	0.14
Diurnal Temperature Range	0.82 ^a	-0.18
Annual Range of Temperature	0.88 ^a	0.05
Mean Elevation	0.71 ^a	-0.16
Maximum Elevation	0.50	-0.55 ^a
% variation explained	43.75	28.10

Loading of environmental variables on phylogenetic principal components 1 and 2 (PC1 and PC2) Cumulative variance explained by PC1 and PC2 is 71.85%. Environmental variables contributing significantly (>0.5) to principal component denoted by ^a

Table S4: Results of phylogenetic generalized least squares models for five response models (mass sexual size dimorphism, wing sexual size dimorphism, tarsus sexual size dimorphism, female average mass, and male average mass).

Response	$\lambda = 1$					$\lambda = 0$				
	Model	$\Delta AICc$	weight	β	95% CI	Model	$\Delta AICc$	weight	β	95% CI
mass ssd	Agility	0.00	0.304	-0.009	-0.018, 0	Agility	0.00	0.560	-0.011	-0.019, -0.003
	PC2	0.66	0.219	0.013	-0.001, 0.028	Agility + PC2	2.35	0.173		
	Agility + PC2	0.71	0.212			Agility + PC1	2.80	0.138		
	Agility + PC1	2.81	0.075			PC2	5.43	0.037	0.009	-0.009, 0.026
	Agility * PC2	3.09	0.065			Agility * PC2	5.74	0.032		
	PC1 + PC2	3.67	0.049			Agility * PC1	6.07	0.027		
	PC1	3.83	0.045	0.001	-0.013, 0.012	PC1	6.40	0.023	0	-0.014, 0.013
	Agility * PC1	5.49	0.019			PC1 + PC2	8.36	0.009		
	PC1 * PC2	6.25	0.13			PC1 * PC2	11.47	0.002		
wing ssd	PC2	0.00	0.545	-0.006	-0.012, -0.001	PC2	0.00	0.284	-0.003	-0.010, 0.004
	PC1 + PC2	2.47	0.159			Agility	0.50	0.222	0	-0.004, 0.003
	Agility + PC2	3.14	0.113			PC1	0.60	0.210	0	-0.005, 0.005
	PC1	4.66	0.053	0.001	-0.004, 0.004	PC1 * PC2	2.31	0.090		
	Agility	4.89	0.047	0	-0.003, 0.004	PC1 + PC2	2.97	0.064		
	PC1 * PC2	4.92	0.047			Agility + PC2	2.97	0.064		
	Agility * PC2	6.37	0.023			Agility + PC1	3.65	0.046		
	Agility + PC1	7.74	0.011			Agility * PC2	6.48	0.011		
	Agility * PC1	10.88	0.002			Agility * PC1	7.20	0.008		
tarsus ssd	PC1	0.00	0.495	0.008	0, 0.015	PC1	0.00	0.367	0.004	-0.003, 0.012
	PC2	0.30	0.158	0.006	0, 0.016	PC2	0.63	0.269	0.004	-0.005, 0.014
	PC1 + PC2	0.62	0.124			Agility	1.50	0.174	0	-0.005, 0.005
	PC1 * PC2	1.81	0.068			PC1 + PC2	3.56	0.062		
	Agility + PC1	2.36	0.059			Agility + PC1	3.79	0.055		
	Agility	3.99	0.035	-0.0002	-0.005, 0.005	Agility + PC2	4.44	0.040		
	Agility + PC2	4.05	0.035			PC1 * PC2	6.12	0.017		
	Agility * PC1	4.84	0.017			Agility * PC1	7.52	0.009		
	Agility * PC2	6.76	0.011			Agility * PC2	7.76	0.008		
female mass	PC1	0.00	0.440	0.385	-0.023, 0.842	PC1	0.00	0.330	0.390	-0.225, 1.006
	PC1 + PC2	1.95	0.166			PC2	1.42	0.162	0.192	-0.645, 1.028
	PC2	2.58	0.121	-0.269	-0.841, 0.304	Agility	1.44	0.160	-0.094	-0.526, 0.338
	Agility + PC1	2.80	0.108			Agility * PC1	2.47	0.088		
	Agility	3.00	0.093	0.023	-0.346, 0.388	Agility + PC1	2.93	0.070		

	PC1 * PC2	5.11	0.032				PC1 + PC2	2.98	0.068		
	Agility + PC2	5.13	0.032				PC1 * PC2	3.00	0.067		
	Agility * PC1	6.18	0.019				Agility + PC2	3.90	0.043		
	Agility * PC2	8.27	0.007				Agility * PC2	7.24	0.008		
male mass	PC1	0.00	0.425	0.373	-0.106, 0.852		Agility	0.00	0.251	-0.251	-0.716, 0.215
	Agility	2.04	0.154	-0.119	-0.512, 0.274		PC1	0.08	0.241	0.357	-0.331, 1.043
	PC2	2.36	0.131	-0.078	-0.709, 0.552		PC2	0.77	0.171	0.293	-0.626, 1.211
	Agility + PC1	2.87	0.101				Agility + PC1	2.17	0.085		
	PC1 + PC2	2.95	0.097				Agility + PC2	2.72	0.064		
	Agility + PC2	4.90	0.037				PC1 * PC2	2.81	0.062		
	PC1 * PC2	5.35	0.029				PC1 + PC2	2.93	0.058		
	Agility * PC1	6.22	0.019				Agility * PC1	2.99	0.056		
	Agility * PC2	8.29	0.007				Agility * PC2	6.11	0.012		

Each response variable was analyzed assuming Brownian motion (Pagel's lambda = 1, strong phylogenetic signal) and no phylogenetic signal (Pagel's lambda = 0). **Response** = variable used as response in model selection. λ = Pagel's lambda for response variable. **Model** = predictor variables of respective model. $\Delta AICc$ = number of AICc units from top model. **weight** = relative model weight. β = slope of relationship between response and predictor variable (only slope for single-effect models is shown for simplicity). **95% CI** = 95% confidence interval for the β parameter of the respective single-effect model. Response variables are abbreviated as follows: Agility = agility score, PC1 = phylogenetic principal component 1 (environmental variation in temperature, elevation), PC2 = phylogenetic principal component 2 (environmental variation in precipitation).

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